

Table 1. Disease index of four diseases and their interaction on BR3 in 1984 aus, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.

Inoculant	Average disease index ^a							
	BB		ShB		ShR		LSc	
	Without ShB	With ShB	Without ShB	With ShB	Without ShB	With ShB	Without ShB	With ShB
0	3.67 d A	2.67 b A	2.67 a B	3.33 e A	0.67 f A	0.33 d A	3.67 d A	2.67 c A
2 (ShR)	2.67 d A	3.00 b A	0.0 c B	5.00 cd A	4.33 b A	4.33 ab A	2.33 e A	3.00 bc A
3 (BB)	6.33 a A	3.00 b B	1.67 ab B	5.00 cd A	2.33 cd A	1.67 c A	5.00 c A	2.67 c B
4 (LSc)	3.00 d A	3.00 b A	0.33 c B	4.33 de A	1.00 ef A	2.00 c A	5.33 bc A	5.00 a A
2, 3	5.00 b A	6.00 a A	0.0 c B	6.33 a A	3.00 c A	3.67 b A	3.67 d A	2.67 c A
2, 4	4.33 c A	2.33 b B	0.0 c B	5.33 bc A	2.67 c A	3.67 b A	5.00 c A	3.67 b B
3, 4	5.00 b A	2.33 b B	0.33 c B	5.83 ab A	1.67 de A	1.67 c A	6.67 a A	5.00 a B
2, 3, 4	5.00 b A	5.33 a A	1.00 b B	6.00 ab A	5.67 a A	4.67 a A	6.00 b A	5.00 a A

^aData are averages of 3 figures based on *Standard evaluation system for rice*. 0 = no disease inoculation, 2 = ShR, 3 = BB, and 4 = LSc. Small letters in a column indicate differences among treatments. Capital letters in a row indicate difference with and without ShB.

Table 2. F values of yield characters of BR3 with multiple disease infection, Joydebpur, Bangladesh.^a

SV	F values		
	Fertile tiller (%)	Filled grain (%)	1,000-grain wt (g)
Multiple infection	2.01 ^{ns}	1.08 ^{ns}	2.13 ^{ns}
No disease vs ShB	12.38**	19.81**	14.54**
Multiple infection × no disease vs ShB	2.12 ^{ns}	1.07 ^{ns}	2.09 ^{ns}
CV %	10.63	11.07	4.11

^aDiseases were ShB, ShR, BB, and LSc. ns = insignificant F value; ** = 1% significant F value.

Plots were inoculated with one to four diseases using a completely randomized design. Subplots were sheath blight (ShB) and no ShB inoculation. Plants were inoculated with ShB and bacterial blight (BB) inocula at maximum tillering, and with sheath rot (ShR) and leaf scald (LSc) at flag leaf stage.

Reactions were significantly different among treatments and with and without ShB (Table I). When LSc infection was high, BB infection was lower. ShB was highest in ShB-inoculated plants and

suppressed the other diseases. ShR was high only when alone, with ShB inoculation, or with inoculation of all diseases. It appeared that ShB did not affect ShR development.

Only ShB was significantly and negatively correlated with fertile tillers, number of filled grains, and 1,000-grain weight ($r = -0.60^*$, -0.81^{**} , and -0.58^*). Of the four diseases, ShB developed fastest and caused the most damage. Values for yield component characters are in Table 2. *ℒ*

Sheath blight (ShB) control

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ShB caused by *Thanatephorus cucumeris* (Frank) Donk is a serious rice disease in Kerala. Under the All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, we evaluated different fungicides for ShB control in a field trial with 1R50. There were seven treatments with four replications in a randomized block design. Plants were inoculated 25 d after planting with ShB pathogen that was multiplied on unhusked rice grains. Fungicides were sprayed 40 and 50 d after planting. Disease incidence and

Chemical control of ShB in 1984-85 kharif, Pattambi, India.

Treatment	Dose/ha	Disease incidence (%)	Disease severity (0-9)
Carbendazim 50 WP (Bavistin)	500 g	29 (31)	3
Carbendazim 50 WP (Jkstein)	500 g	24 (29)	2
Thiophanate 70 WP	500 g	30 (33)	2
Mancozeb 75 WP	1250 g	37 (38)	4
Validamycin 3L	1000 ml	13 (21)	1
IBP 48 EC	500 ml	343 (36)	
Check (unsprayed)	—	81 (65)	9
CD (0.05)		(11)	1
CV (%)		19	21

severity were measured by counting infected tillers from 10 randomly selected hills from each plot and scored using the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.

All the fungicides checked ShB intensity (see table). Validamycin 3L at 1 litre/ha and carbendazim 500 g/ha performed similarly and significantly better than other treatments (see table). *ℒ*

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